

D1.3

Initial Data Management Plan

Work Package	1
Lead partner	FZJ
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Deliverable abstract

The Data Management Plan (DMP) contains information on the suggested policies, standards, and sustainability activities related to the created data services, including software solutions for the services. This is done in close collaboration with the work packages on FAIR Policies and common technical solutions, to ensure the management of knowledge in the project is maintained following the FAIR principles.

The DMP covers the data, documents and solutions created within the project (i.e. not the data provided by the RIs in their services, which is part of their service policies). It describes the data (including metadata) and software standards, availability, curation and preservation methods, and is based on the Digital Curation Centre model for DMPs.

The initial DMP focuses on the tools and systems which are used to maintain personal data of involved project participants. The plan will be updated annually.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner Organization	Date
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DELIVERY LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
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V 0.2	27 June 2019	Revised version sent for approval	A. Petzold
V 1.0	29 June 2019	Final version submitted	A. Petzold

DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

TERMINOLOGY

A relevant project terminology is included as an Appendix.

The latest version of the master list of the terminology is here:
<https://confluence.egi.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=14452608>

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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Preamble

Rationale

The Data Management Plan (DMP) contains information on the suggested policies, standards, and sustainability activities related to the created data services, including software solutions for the services. This is done in close collaboration with the work packages on FAIR Policies and common technical solutions, to ensure the management of knowledge in the project is maintained following the FAIR principles.

The DMP covers the data, documents and solutions created within the project (i.e. not the data provided by the RIs in their services, which is the part of the service policies). It describes the data (including metadata) and software standards, availability, curation and preservation methods, and is based on the Digital Curation Centre model for DMPs accessible at <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>.

The initial DMP focuses on the tools and systems which are used to maintain personal data of involved project participants. The plan will be updated annually. Subsequent updates of the DMP will then include the description of data and metadata, software standards, availability, curation and preservation methods used for the data, documents and solutions created within the project.

Data Management Team

The Data Management Team is responsible for providing ENVRI-FAIR with Data Management Plans (DMP) during the project period and oversees the DMP revision.

The management team consists of the Co-coordinator (chair), Project Management Team (PMT) representative, responsible of drafting the DMP text, and WP 5 and 7 leaders. The General Assembly (GA) confirms the membership of Data Management Team during annual GA meeting.

DMT Members confirmed by the GA:

Ari Asmi (co-coordinator)	ari.asmi@helsinki.fi
Daniela Franz (PMT representative)	d.franz@fz-juelich.de
Alex Vermeulen (WP 5 lead)	alex.vermeulen@icos-ri.eu
Zhiming Zhao (WP 7 lead)	z.zhao@uva.nl

DMT Member proposed to GA

Ulrich Bundke (ENVRI-FAIR data manager)	u.bundke@fz-juelich.de
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The initial DMP is produced as a deliverable of WP1 and subsequent annual updates will be also delivered via WP1.

Initial Data Management Plan

1. Data Summary

Potential data assets generated by the project are:

- Personal contact data
- Project documents
- Surveys, questionnaires
- Digital objects created via the use case studies defined the work packages
- Geophysical data sets collected via the RIs during the project
- Software

In its initial phase the project data collection and management is exclusively related to personal data of project participants and of members of the ENVRI community. Participation to the project is granted by invitation or on personal request.

Personal contact data are collected during the login request by the users. After access has been granted, the user can maintain own personal data individually.

Lists of participants to general project meetings and to work package meetings are collected on site and are kept as internal documents in the respective work package storages of the Redmine environment used for the project management and internal communication.

Results from internal surveys of target groups are stored in the respective work package storages.

Storage and stewardship of digital objects, software, and geophysical data sets will be described in the next subsequent updates of the Data Management Plan.

2. FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In the initial phase of the project, personal contact data and participation of the individuals to project work packages and working groups is stored. No further information or other metadata is stored.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

It is not intended to making the personal contact data of the project participants and data from internal surveys openly accessible.

2.3 Making data interoperable

It is not intended to making the personal contact data of the project participants and data from internal surveys available for external use and analyses.

2.4 Increase data re-use

Not applicable.

3. Allocation of Resources

ENVRI-FAIR uses the open-source Redmine environment (www.redmine.org) for storage of project-related contact information of participants and project-related documents. The system is a password-protected and secured system for project data storage. The access is controlled, and can be specified for specific times.

Redmine is a free and open source, web-based project management and issue tracking tool. It allows users to manage multiple projects and associated subprojects. It features per project wikis and forums, time tracking, and flexible, role-based access control. It includes a calendar and Gantt charts to aid visual representation of projects and their deadlines. Redmine integrates with various version control systems and includes a repository browser and a document comparison tool (diff viewer).

The implemented Document Management System Features include directory structure, document versioning and revision history, email notifications for directories and/or documents, document locking, configurable document approval workflow, document access auditing and document content full text search.

Project participants use the internal Redmine environment for communication and sharing of documents. This ensures that communication and related documents are stored in the Redmine archive and can be accessed throughout the lifetime of the project. Redmine includes version control of documents and keeps the previous versions so that continuing version control is in place.

The Redmine system is hosted at Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH and administrated by the ENVRI-FAIR data manager Ulrich Bundke, email u.bundke@fz-juelich.de. The ENVRI-FAIR data manager is responsible for the implementation of the DMP and related data management activities. The Data Management Team is responsible for the review and of the DMP and oversees the DMP revision.

Hardware resources required for the delivery of the DMP are provided in-kind by Forschungszentrum Juelich. Staff resources are covered by project funding.

The Redmine system will be kept online minimum one year after the project. This period can be extended on request by the ENVRI community to ensure the continuation of the ENVRI-FAIR work after the project lifetime.

4. Data Security

The Redmine environment is hosted at a local Linux cluster of the Institute of Energy and Climate Research 8 of Forschungszentrum Juelich which is coordinating the project.

The Linux cluster is backed up daily by the IT Services of Forschungszentrum Juelich.

The personal contact data of the project participants and data from internal surveys will be maintained and kept accessible in the Redmine environment during the lifetime of the project.

Personal information contained in surveys is destroyed latest on the project end, preferably immediately after the conclusions of the study are finalized.

5. Ethical Aspects

Based on the self-assessment presented in the ENVRI-FAIR document D12.1 "POPD Requirement No. 1"¹, ENVRI-FAIR involves processing of personal data only on the level of collecting contact information of participants to meetings and workshops, and within a survey of target groups' needs; participants will be provided in writing with details of what personal information will be processed and with other relevant information on processing of their personal data as required by General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation EU 2016/679).

Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH ensures the required ENVRI-FAIR related file keeping of

- detailed information on the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, an destruction, and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation;
- detailed information on the informed consent procedures in regard to the collection, storage, and protection of personal data;
- templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets.

6. Other

Further details of the procedures for data management used in ENVRI-FAIR are described in

- ENVRI-FAIR D12.1 POPD Requirement No. 1
- Declaration of Conformity with Requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of Natural Persons with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data and the Free Movement of such Data, and Repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation); issued by FZ Juelich data Protection Officer in July 2018 (Appendix to ENVRI-FAIR D12.1)

¹ The self-assessment was prepared according to the Ethics Self-Assessment Guidance: Horizon 2020 Guidance — How to complete your ethics self-assessment: V6.1 – 04.02.2019

Appendices

List of Acronyms

BEERi	Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures - is an internal advisory board representing the needs of environmental Research Infrastructures
CA	Consortium Agreement - Legal contract between the ENVRI-FAIR beneficiaries
DL	Deliverable / Deadline
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMT	Data Management Team
DoA	Description of Action
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EB	Executive Board - supervisory body for the execution of the Project
EC	European Commission - is the executive body of the European Union responsible for proposing legislation, implementing decisions, upholding the EU treaties and managing the day-to-day business of the EU
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GA	(1) Grant Agreement - Contract between Coordinator and Commission (2) General Assembly - GA is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JSC	Juelich Supercomputing Centre
PM	Person Month
PMT	Project Management Team
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
PWG	Policy Working Group
RI	Research Infrastructure
ToR	Terms of Reference
WP	Work Package